

Psychological Morbidity among Different Healthcare Workers during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Hospital Based Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Background: COVID-19 pandemic was declared as an international public health emergency by World Health Organization in January 2020. High infectivity and mortality rate was a great concern for all. The frontline healthcare professionals (HCPs) were at the risk of developing infection following direct contact with Covid-19 infected patients.

Objectives: To evaluate the psychological morbidity among different healthcare workers during Covid-19 pandemic.

Methodology: This cross-sectional study was conducted at Diphu Medical College & Hospital from April 2020 to Sept 2020 covering 98 healthcare workers. Data were collected once in a week following Covid protocol using self-administered questionnaire. Socio-demographic profile and anxiety, stress and depressive symptoms were assessed by using Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21). Chi-square test and other inferential statistics were used to analyze data.

Results: Study showed, the prevalence rates of anxiety, stress and depression were respectively 63.3%, 18.4%, and 44.9%. Higher literacy was directly proportional to psychiatric morbidity. Female gender and nurses had more psychiatric morbidity compared to other study groups.

Conclusion: Prior to pandemic situation, context specific programme strategies and policies are utmost necessary to protect healthcare workers to minimize psychiatric morbidity.

Keywords: COVID-19, Anxiety, Stress, Depression, Healthcare Workers, Assam.

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Introduction

Despite an extensive healthcare system, the Covid-19 pandemic had a massive impact upon the existing Indian healthcare system. Most of the organizations and various government departments encouraged their employees to 'work from home', however, such provisions were not possible for healthcare workers (HCWs). Increased workload, physical and psychological exhaustion, mental unpreparedness, reduced availability of trained personnel, scarcity of the personal protective equipment (PPEs), oxygen availability, risk of infection to self and infection to others, posed a complex environment, leading to a substantial impact on psychological health among healthcare workers [1,2,3]. A study on men-

tal health impact of Covid-19 on doctors (n = 152) in West Bengal showed that 39.5%, 33% and 34.9% doctors had anxiety, stress and depressive symptoms respectively [4].

Available data from different studies done during the various epidemics and current Covid-19 pandemic among HCWs showed that the prevalence of anxiety symptoms ranges from 10.5% to 44.6%, with a pooled prevalence of 23.2% and the prevalence of depression rate varied from 8.9% to 50.4%, with the pooled prevalence of 22.8% [5]. In other studies, among the doctors and nurses showed

pooled prevalence 17.9% for mild anxiety and 6.9% for moderate to severe anxiety [6,7].

COVID-19 pandemic affected almost all countries of the world with various of morbidity and mortality. Lots of information and misinformation circulated within a short period of time. This led to fear and panic amongst all, including the frontline healthcare workers against this pandemic. Major morbidity and mortality associated with this newly emerged disease was a probable reason for fear and panic among all healthcare workers. In this background, we have decided to conduct the current study in a newly established tertiary care centre, where limited infrastructure and resources were available. This study with an aim to evaluate the psychological morbidity among different HCWs.

Materials and Methods:

This hospital based cross-sectional study was conducted covering all healthcare workers involved in Covid-19 screening, Covid ward and Covid ICU duty at Diphu Medical College & Hospital, Karbi Anglong, Assam. The study was conducted from April 2020 to Sept 2020 covering 38 doctors, 21 nurses and 38 numbers of other health care workers (n = 98). Doctors, nursing staff and other healthcare workers, who were directly involved with patient care were included in the study. Those staffs, like hospital administration, general office staff etc. who were not directly involved in patient care and those who were not willing to participate

in the study were excluded. As the healthcare workers were posted in Covid ward and Covid screening duties for a period of one week, we visited the ward once in a week following Covid protocol to collect the data. Before collecting any data, informed consent was obtained from all study participants. Socio-demographic information and anxiety, stress and depressive symptoms were assessed by distributing standardized self-administered questionnaire using Depression, Anxiety and Stress Scale (DASS-21), developed by researchers Lovibond and Lovibond at the University of New South Wales (1995). This is a screening tool containing 21 questionnaires consisting of 7 questions each for anxiety, stress and depression.

The depression sub-scale assesses hopelessness, dysphoria, devaluation of life, self-deprecation, anhedonia, lack of interest / involvement and inertia. The anxiety sub-scale assesses autonomic arousal, situational anxiety, skeletal muscle effects, and subjective experience of anxious affect. Stress sub-scale assesses difficulty in relaxing, nervous arousal, and being easily upset/agitated, impatient and irritable/over-reactive. Total scores for depression, anxiety and stress are calculated by summing the scores for the relevant items. Each item of the scale can be scored from 0 to 3 according to the response. It is to be noted that scores of each subscale need to be multiplied by 2 to get the final score. Scoring pattern of each subscale of DASS-21 [8] is shown in table-1.

Table 1: Scoring of Depression, Anxiety and Stress Symptoms using DASS-21

	Depression	Anxiety	Stress
Normal	0-9	0-7	0-14
Mild	10-13	8-9	15-18
Moderate	14-20	10-14	19-25
Severe	21-27	15-19	26-33
Extremely severe	28+	20+	34+

Statistical Methods: SPSS.24 was used for data analysis which includes chi-square test and other inferential statistics.

Ethical consideration and consent: Ethical approval was obtained from the Institutional Ethics

Committee, DMCH, Karbi Anglong, Assam before initiation of the study. Written informed consent was obtained from each participant. Confidentiality was strictly maintained.

Results

Table 2: Background Characteristics

Number of Respondents ▶	No of Respondents (n = 98)	Percentage (%)
Background Characteristics ▼		
Age (in years)		
16-25	18	18.4
26-35	44	44.9
36-45	17	17.3
46-55	15	15.3
56-65	4	4.1
Gender		
Male	50	51
Female	48	49

Types of Family		
Nuclear	62	63.3
Joint	32	32.7
Extended family	4	4.0
Education Level		
Primary school	2	2
High school	6	6.1
Higher secondary school	14	14.3
College level	15	15.3
University level	3	3.1
Professional/ technical	58	59.2
Types of Profession		
Doctor	38	38.8
Nurse	21	21.4
Other Health Care Workers	39	39.8

Table 2 depicts baseline characteristic of our study population. Around 51% of our sample were male and 49% female. Regarding family types, around 63% came from nuclear family, 33% from joint family and 4% from extended family. Majority

(45%) of our study population were between 26 to 35 years age group followed by 16 to 25 years, 36 to 45 years and 46 to 55 years. In this study, 39% were doctors, 21% nurses and remaining 40% were other healthcare workers.

Table 3: Anxiety symptoms among Healthcare Workers during COVID-19 Pandemic.

Anxiety (Sub Scale) Variables	Normal (n = 36)	Mild (n = 18)	Moderate (n = 26)	Severe (n = 9)	Extremely Severe (n = 9)	P Value
Age (in years)						
16-25	5(27.8%)	3(16.7%)	5(27.8%)	2(11.1%)	3(16.7%)	0.887
26-35	15(34.1%)	11(25%)	11(25%)	4(9.1%)	3(6.8%)	
36-45	7(41.2%)	3(17.6%)	4(23.5%)	1(5.9%)	2(11.8%)	
46-55	8(53.3%)	0(0%)	4(26.7%)	2(13.3%)	1(6.7%)	
56-65	1(25%)	1(25%)	2(50%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Gender						
Male	20(40%)	10(20%)	10(20%)	7(14%)	3(6%)	0.215
Female	16(33.3%)	8(16.7%)	16(33.3%)	2(4.2%)	6(12.5%)	
Types of Family						
Nuclear	22(35.5%)	10(16.1%)	16(25.8%)	9(14.5%)	5(8.1%)	0.063
Joint	12(37.5%)	8(25%)	8(25%)	0(0%)	4(12.5%)	
Extended family	2(50%)	0(0%)	2(50%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Education Level						
Primary school	0(0%)	0(0%)	2(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0.268
High school	3(50%)	2(33.3%)	1(16.7%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
H.S. school	7(50%)	4(28.6%)	3(21.4%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
College level	2(13.3%)	5(33.3%)	4(26.7%)	2(13.3%)	2(13.3%)	
University level	1(33.3%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(33.3%)	1(33.3%)	
Professional/ technical	23(39.7%)	7(12.1%)	16(27.6%)	6(10.3%)	6(10.3%)	
Types of Profession						
Doctor	17(44.7%)	4(10.5%)	9(23.7%)	6(15.8%)	2(5.3%)	0.063
Nurse	5(23.8%)	3(14.3%)	7(33.3%)	1(4.8%)	5(23.8%)	
Other Health Care Workers	14(35.9%)	11(28.2%)	10(25.6%)	2(5.1%)	2(5.1%)	

In this study, females were found to have extremely severe anxiety symptoms as compared to males as

depicted in Table 3. Severe and extremely severe anxiety symptoms were observed more among 16

to 25 years age group whereas 46 to 55 years age group had less anxiety symptoms. Among healthcare workers having university or postgraduate degree, severe and extremely severe

anxiety symptoms were found to be more. However no statistically significant difference was observed between education level and level of anxiety symptoms.

Table 4: Level of Stress among Healthcare Workers during COVID-19 Pandemic.

Stress▶ (Sub Scale)	Normal (n = 80)	Mild (n = 8)	Moderate (n = 7)	Severe (n = 3)	P Value
Variables ▼					
Age (in years)					
16-25	13(72.2%)	2(11.1%)	1(5.6%)	2(11.1%)	0.77
26-35	37(84.1%)	4(9.1%)	2(4.5%)	1(2.3%)	
36-45	14(82.4%)	1(5.9%)	2(11.8%)	0(0%)	
46-55	12(80%)	1(6.7%)	2(13.3%)	0(0%)	
56-65	4(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Gender					
Male	40(80%)	6(12%)	3(6%)	1(2%)	0.487
Female	40(83.3%)	2(4.2%)	4(8.3%)	2(4.2%)	
Types of Family					
Nuclear	48(77.4%)	8(12.9%)	4(6.5%)	2(3.2%)	0.764
Joint	28(87.5%)	0(0%)	3(9.4%)	1(3.1%)	
Extended family	4(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Education Level					
Primary school	2(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0.179
High school	6(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
H.S. school	14(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
College level	11(73.3%)	2(13.3%)	1(6.7%)	1(6.7%)	
University level	1(33.3%)	1(33.3%)	0(0%)	1(33.3%)	
Professional/ technical	46(79.3%)	5(8.6%)	6(10.3%)	1(1.7%)	
Types of Profession					
Doctor	30(78.9%)	5(13.2%)	3(7.9%)	0(0%)	0.16
Nurse	15(71.4%)	1(4.8%)	3(14.3%)	2(9.5%)	
Other Healthcare Workers	35(89.7%)	2(5.1%)	1(2.6%)	1(2.6%)	

It was observed from table 4 that overall, one fifth of the healthcare personnel had symptoms related to stress. No significant difference of stress level was observed according to gender. Extremely severe stress was found to be more among 16 to 25 years age group whereas a greater number of 46 to

55 years age group had more moderate depressive symptoms. Overall healthcare professional with postgraduate qualifications had more symptoms of stress as compared to other healthcare personnel. However, all these findings were not statistically significant.

Table 5: Depressive Symptoms among Healthcare Workers during Covid-19 Pandemic.

Depression▶ (Sub Scale)	Normal (n = 54)	Mild (n = 24)	Moderate (n = 13)	Severe (n = 4)	Extremely Severe (n = 3)	P Value
Variables ▼						
Age (in years)						
16-25	8 (44.4%)	5 (27.8%)	2 (11.1%)	1 (5.6%)	2 (11.1%)	0.885
26-35	26 (59.1%)	11 (25%)	5 (11.4%)	1 (2.3%)	1 (2.3%)	
36-45	10 (58.8%)	3 (17.6%)	3 (17.6%)	1 (5.9%)	0 (0%)	
46-55	8 (53.3%)	3 (20%)	3 (20%)	1 (6.7%)	0 (0%)	
56-65	2 (50%)	2 (50%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	
Gender						
Male	30(60%)	8(16%)	10(20%)	1(2%)	1(2%)	0.078
Female	24(50%)	16(33.3%)	3(6.3%)	3(6.3%)	2(4.2%)	
Types of Family						
Nuclear	32(51.6%)	15(24.2%)	11(17.7%)	2(3.2%)	2(3.2%)	0.956

Joint	20(62.5%)	7(21.9%)	2(6.3%)	2(6.3%)	1(3.1%)	
Extended family	2(50%)	2(50%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
Education Level						
Primary school	0(0%)	2(100%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0.111
High school	5(83.3%)	0(0%)	1(16.7%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
H.S. school	11(78.6%)	3(21.4%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	
College level	7(46.7%)	4(26.7%)	3(20%)	0(0%)	1(6.7%)	
University level	1(33.3%)	0(0%)	1(33.3%)	0(0%)	1(33.3%)	
Professional/ technical	30(51.7%)	15(25.9%)	8(13.8%)	4(6.9%)	1(1.7%)	
Types of Profession						
Doctor	21(55.3%)	8(21.1%)	8(21.1%)	1(2.6%)	0(0%)	0.031
Nurse	8(38.1%)	7(33.3%)	1(4.8%)	3(14.3%)	2(9.5%)	
Other Healthcare Workers	25(64.1%)	9(23.1%)	4(10.3%)	0(0%)	1(2.6%)	

Table 5 depicts that mild depressive reactions were more common, however in moderate depression males more commonly were affected as compared to female counterpart. This difference was not statistically significant. Depressive symptoms were less common among doctors as compared to nurses and other paramedical staffs. This difference was found to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). In this study 2 elderly persons were found to be mildly depressed and whereas severe depression was found to be more common among 16 to 25 years age group. Mild and moderate depressive reactions were more common among 36 to 45 years age group. Extremely severe depressive symptoms were more common amongst postgraduates, whereas a greater number of healthcare workers having professional qualifications had mild depressive symptoms.

Discussion:

The first COVID-19 case was detected in India on January 30, 2020, in Kerala. Government of India announced lockdown by March 25, 2020, for a period of 21 days which was later extended [9]. The first Covid-19 case of Assam was reported on 31 March 2020 [10]. The North-East region of India, which consists of seven states, rank one of the lowest in terms of health-care infrastructure. However, during lockdown period government of Assam took prompt initiative in strengthening the health care infrastructure to manage cases at different level including intensive care units (ICU). Government also took several measures to train and capacity building for HCWs. Based on previous experience of successfully managing epidemics and pandemics, Govt. of India provided requisites strategies, plans and procedures, which included guideline related to behavioural, psychosocial health inspirational guidance for HCWs [11].

This study aimed to find out the anxiety, stress and depressive symptoms among the frontline HCWs. The fear of infection to self and family resulted in the frontliners more susceptible to anxiety, stress

and depression during the pandemic. In this study, it has been observed that majority of study participants had mild anxiety symptoms (26.5%) out of which female were more affected. We also observed that nurses exhibited more anxiety symptoms as compared to other study participants. Similarly, Sharma R et al. showed that female HCWs were more anxious (82.8%) compared to male [12]. Raj R et al. and Sukumaran AB et al. showed that nurses exhibited more anxiety symptoms as compared to doctors which corroborates our findings [13,14]. In our study, anxiety symptoms among HCWs were 63.3%. In contrary to our findings, Sharma Pet al. showed only 7.5% HCWs had anxiety symptoms [15] and Gupta S et al. and Zhang C et al. in their study showed 37.2% and 44.6% study participants had anxiety symptoms respectively [16,17].

The current study showed only 8.2%, 7.1% and 3.1% participants had mild, moderate and severe stress respectively. It was also observed that male participants had more stress as compared to females. In contrary to our findings Sharma R et al. highlighted that due to staying away from home, family dysfunction, and long working hours more in front-line HCWs were more anxious and stressed compared to others [12]. Sukumaran AB et al. in their study did not observe any statistical difference in stress and depression score in different professionals which corroborate to our findings [14]. Literacy status showed negative impact on Covid related psychological symptoms. Similar to our finding Fakhari A et al. in their study revealed negative correlation between mental health literacy and Covid-19 related stress [18]. Cai H et al. also showed more emotional stress during Covid-19 pandemic amongst doctors. They stated that the medical fraternity was extremely worried about passing the infection to their family members [1].

In this study, half of the study participants had depressive symptoms as per DASS-21 scale, of which 24.5%, 13.3% and 7.4% had mild, moderate and severe depressive symptoms respectively. Females

had more depressive symptoms as compared to male. Similar to our findings Zhang C et al. also reported half of the participants (50.4%) had symptoms of depression [17]. However, Gupta S et al. showed approximately one-third of the HCWs reported anxiety and depressive symptoms [16]. Sharma SK et al. in their meta-analysis identified that the pooled estimates of depression, anxiety, and stress among Indian HCWs during the Covid-19 pandemic were 20.1%, 25.0%, and 36%, respectively [19]. It was observed that doctors and those who have higher education level had more depressive symptoms as compared to other study participants. However, this difference was statistically insignificant. Similarly, Sukumaran AB et al. also did not find any significant difference in stress and depression scores between different professional categories [14].

The present study had certain limitations, which include small sample size covering only frontline HCWs. The present study did not evaluate other factors like social support, training received or not, any extra compensation received or not for Covid duties, history of previous physical or psychological disorders and self-stigma etc. Further, the current study also did not evaluate any personality dimension, sleep disorders, coping skills, substance dependence, and duration of duty hours. All these variables can influence the prevalence of psychiatric morbidity during Covid-19 pandemic.

Conclusions:

The current study showed that the prevalence rates of anxiety, stress and depressive symptoms were 63.3%, 18.4%, and 44.9%, respectively. Psychiatric morbidity was mainly in the form of issues related to anxiety. No significant statistical difference observed amongst different professional groups. Higher literacy was directly proportional to psychiatric morbidity. Female gender and nurses had more psychiatric morbidity as compared to others. There is need of a context specific programme strategies and policies to protect these frontline HCWs before and during the pandemic situation to minimize psychiatric morbidity.

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